

High Humidity Roll-to-Roll Coating of Wide-bandgap CsFAPbBr₃-based Perovskite Solar Cells via Optimized Ink Formulation

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Abstract

The growing demand for sustainable energy solutions has made the development of scalable, efficient, and cost-effective perovskite solar cells (PSCs) increasingly important. Wide bandgap PSCs are currently behind conventional PSCs in upscaling, with limited success in printing wide bandgap PSCs. Wide-bandgap perovskites stand out due to their efficiency in low-light conditions and their use in tandem solar cells. Developing upscaling methods is essential to fully realize their potential in the renewable energy sector. This research addresses the development of roll-to-roll (R2R) slot-die coating of Cs_{0.05}FA_{0.95}PbBr₃-based wide bandgap perovskites by focusing on improving the film formation process and ink formulation. By adding optimal concentration of CsBr and performing in-situ characterization, we obtain Cs_{0.05}FA_{0.95}PbBr₃ films with enhanced morphology and crystallinity in high humidity conditions (50% RH), without inducing secondary phase formation. In addition, slot-die coating defects are eliminated through introducing the non-toxic DMSO: Butanol (9:1) solvent system. The roll-to-roll coated wide-bandgap PSCs reaches a power conversion efficiency (PCE) of up to 8.97%. The corresponding roll-to-roll coated modules with a 5 × 5 cm² active area achieve a PCE of 5.8%, representing a crucial step towards the high-throughput, cost-effective production of perovskite solar modules.

Keywords: Roll-to-Roll (R2R), Slot-die Coating, Wide-bandgap Perovskite Solar Cells, Ink Formulation, Ambient Deposition

1. Introduction

The global quest for sustainable energy resources has placed solar energy at the forefront due to its abundant supply, emphasizing the need to develop low-cost and scalable photovoltaic technologies. Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) offer notable advantages such as excellent optoelectronic properties^[1,2], affordability^[3,4], and relatively simple production processes^[5]. Perovskites have seen remarkable improvements in power conversion efficiency (PCE), rising from 3.8% to over 26% in a short time^[6]. This rapid progress highlights the potential of perovskites to revolutionize photovoltaic technologies, emphasizing the need to tackle scalability issues to fully unlock the potential of PSCs^[7]. A beneficial feature of perovskites is their tunable bandgap by composition engineering^[8,9]. Recently, wide bandgap perovskite materials like FAPbBr₃ have attracted interest due to their unique applications requiring transparency^[9–13], in tandem solar cells^[14], in low-light environments such as under-water solar cells^[15], X-ray detectors^[16], and photocatalytic applications^[17]. Upscaling wide-bandgap PSCs offers a promising opportunity for commercializing all-perovskite tandem solar cells and provides a method for incorporating perovskites into current photovoltaic technologies, representing a major step toward commercial viability of cost-effective tandem photovoltaics^[18].

The slot-die coating of FAPbBr₃ remains underexplored in current literature, presenting a gap in perovskite research, particularly regarding their integration into roll-to-roll manufacturing processes. Spin-coating, a simple and effective method that is widely used for small-scale devices falls short for mass production due to its limited scalability and high material wastage^[19,20]. For scalable manufacturing, researchers have investigated alternative deposition techniques such as blade coating^[21,22], slot-die coating^[23,24], inkjet printing^[25], screen printing^[26,27], and spray-coating^[28,29]. Blade coating and slot-die coating, referred to as meniscus coating techniques, stand out for their versatility, efficiency, scalability, and compatibility with R2R manufacturing processes^[30–32]. R2R slot-die coating offers a promising solution for scaling up the production of flexible perovskite solar cells, particularly attractive for its potential in large-scale, high-throughput, and low-cost manufacturing^[24,33,34]. However, applying slot-die coating to perovskite films comes with challenges, including the need for precise control over ink formulation and processing conditions.^[23,35] Most studies have focused on narrower bandgap perovskites, chosen for their higher efficiency in single-junction devices, hence, there is no literature on the slot-die coating of FAPbBr₃-based PSCs.

Another aspect to consider in the scalability of PSCs is the ability to be deposited in ambient conditions to simplify the process and lower manufacturing costs. High humidity negatively impacts the growth and crystallization of perovskite films^[36–38]. A method for fabricating scalable PSCs in ambient conditions involves using a two-step deposition process^[10,22,39,40]. The two-step deposition simplifies controlling the crystallization dynamics compared to one-step deposition methods, allowing for the formation of high-quality lead halide films before converting to perovskite^[41,42]. Studies have shown that this method is less sensitive to humidity, and adverse effects of moisture can be reduced by adding AX (A= organic cation) salts to the PbX₂ ink, since moderate humidity can positively affect the conversion of lead halide to the perovskite phase in the presence of these additives^[10,39,42]. In addition, unlike the single-step deposition of FAPbBr₃

perovskite which requires annealing temperatures above 150 °C, the two-step deposition method only requires temperatures as low as 80 °C [10]. Processing at low temperatures offers benefits, such as lower energy consumption and the possibility of using flexible substrates. Therefore, using a two-step deposition method enables the ambient air deposition of flexible FAPbBr₃-based perovskite solar cells.

The scaling-up of PSCs using highly toxic solvents like dimethyl formamide (DMF), N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), and 2-Methoxyethanol (2-Me) can present serious environmental risks. For instance, producing 1 GW of PSCs through blade coating is estimated to emit 3,500 liters of solvents^[43]. Consequently, mass production of PSCs releasing thousands of liters of solvents into the environment is subject to restrictions by legislation. [4,44,45]. Therefore, it is crucial to develop methods for creating large-area PSCs with safer solvents. Life cycle analysis proved Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) as a preferable option compared to other common polar aprotic solvents used in PSCs fabrication due to its lower impact on the environment and human health [46]. Moreover, DMSO has proven to be an effective solvent for PbX₂ in two-step blade coating of PSCs^[10,39].

This study focuses on filling the research gap in R2R slot-die coating for FAPbBr₃-based wide bandgap perovskites. Firstly, we investigated the effect of CsBr additive to the two-step doctor blading of the FAPbBr₃ perovskite in high humidity conditions (50% RH) by examining the perovskite phase formation process with in-situ photoluminescence (PL) and UV-Visible characterization. Secondly, we introduced butanol as a co-solvent to the DMSO-based ink formulation to enhance the wettability and fluid dynamics of the perovskite solution. These strategies resulted in improved film uniformity and crystallinity, leading to enhanced efficiency of R2R slot-die coated PSCs. Our findings open routes towards upscaling PSCs in ambient air using non-toxic solvent systems.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. The Role of CsBr Additive

The two-step deposition of FAPbBr₃ perovskite consisted of the blade coating of PbBr₂, followed by conversion to the perovskite phase by blade coating of FABr. This method effectively deposits perovskite under ambient conditions using a non-toxic, DMSO-based solvent^[10,39,42]. Films were compared across four conditions: pristine, and addition of 5%, 10%, and 15% CsBr to the first step ink. Concentrations above 15% CsBr were impractical due to limited solubility of CsBr in DMSO (**Figure S3**). **Figures 1a** and **1b** present the XRD patterns of PbBr₂ and FAPbBr₃ films, respectively, modified by varying CsBr concentrations.

As depicted in the XRD patterns in **Figure 1a**, pristine PbBr₂ films exhibit a crystalline structure with the presence of a PbBr₂-DMSO intermediate phase. Introduction of 5% CsBr converts the structure to an amorphous state, while higher concentrations (10% and 15%) lead to the formation of CsPbBr₃ peaks, also identifiable by a color change in the film from transparent to

pale yellow for the 15% CsBr sample. The XRD peaks in **Figure 1b** confirm the presence of the FAPbBr_3 perovskite phase, with peaks at specific 2θ values representing [100], [110], and [200] Miller indices for all samples^[47]. However, the addition of CsBr causes a minor shift in these peaks towards higher 2θ values (**Table S1**), indicative of slight lattice distortion, a finding consistent with literature^[48].

Figure 1. (a) XRD patterns of PbBr_2 films with CsBr concentrations of 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15%. (b) XRD patterns of perovskite films with the same CsBr concentrations. SEM images showing the surface morphology of (c) PbBr_2 and (d) perovskite films at these concentrations.

For CsBr concentrations exceeding 10%, the emergence of a new phase, Cs_4PbBr_6 ^[49], is observed in the perovskite film. The SEM images in Figures 1c and 1d validate the influence of CsBr on the film morphology. Specifically, the addition of 5% CsBr introduces voids in the PbBr_2 film (**Figure 1c**), enhancing FAPr diffusion and improving perovskite crystallization as evidenced by more defined grain structures in subsequent images (**Figure 1d**). However, increasing the CsBr

concentration to 10% and 15% alters the morphology, likely due to phase segregation of CsPbBr₃, as also noted in the XRD patterns. At the highest CsBr concentration, the film exhibits an irregular morphology, suggesting a heterogeneous Cs distribution.

The SEM images of the corresponding perovskite films (**Figure 1d**) further reveal that a 5% CsBr concentration resulted in optimal morphology, larger crystal grains and potentially superior optical properties. As evidenced by the XRD patterns, this concentration minimizes the presence of secondary phase competition seen at higher concentration.

In order to monitor film formation and crystallization dynamics under varying conditions of CsBr additive concentration, an in-situ UV-vis absorption and PL spectroscopy system was implemented. We tracked perovskite formation by coating the FAPbBr₃ solution on a substrate pre-coated with PbBr₂ and different concentrations of CsBr as shown in **Figure 2a**. In-situ PL measurements are depicted in **Figure 2b**. The pristine sample started with broad PL emission that could correspond to the poor morphology and presence of defects. The PL intensity shifts toward 540 nm overtime that corresponds to FAPbBr₃ phase. However, the peak is relatively broad indicating the structural disorder within the film. With the addition of 5% CsBr, the in-situ PL results reveal immediate signs of perovskite crystal formation. With increasing CsBr content to 10% and above, the presence of a 540 nm signal characteristic of FAPbBr₃, is delayed and a weak early 520 nm signal, indicative of CsPbBr₃ formation^[49], appears in the initial PbBr₂ layer. This suggests that the CsBr additive significantly influences the crystallization dynamics of FAPbBr₃ during the second step. The excessive additive concentrations lead to early CsPbBr₃ formation in the first layer (as confirmed by the XRD patterns in **Figure 1a**), which can interfere with further crystallization through cation exchange^[50].

The in-situ UV-vis results (**Figure 1c**) complement the PL findings by indicating the crystallization rates. Without additives, the absorption spectrum gradually evolves, indicating a slow crystallization rate. Additionally, the final absorption spectrum does not show the maximum at 525 nm which is in line with the broad PL peak and confirms the poor morphology showed in SEM images. Also, the final absorption spectrum for 15% CsBr film follows the same trend and confirms the poor film morphology. With a 5% CsBr concentration, there is a noticeable acceleration in crystallization. However, beyond this concentration, the crystallization initiation slows down, suggesting that higher levels of CsBr act more as inhibitors rather than facilitators of crystallization. Hence, 5% CsBr additive enhanced grain size, leading to the formation of more uniformly structured perovskite films. In contrast, the absence of additives or excessive concentrations hinder the process, lead to uneven perovskite layers. We identified 5% CsBr as the optimal additive level. This perovskite formulation, Cs_{0.05}FA_{0.95}PbBr₃, will be used in the subsequent sections.

Figure 2. (a) The schematic of the in-situ PL and UV-Visible analysis of blade coating perovskite on glass. (b) The in-situ PL and (c) The in-situ UV-Visible absorption spectra of FAPbBr₃ perovskite films with the variation of CsBr additive (0%, 5%, 10%, and 15%).

2.2. Roll-to-roll Slot-die Coating Process

To streamline the production of PSCs and enhance their commercial viability, we have transitioned from a laboratory scale two-step blade coating process to a two-step R2R slot-die coating process. The R2R slot-die coating process is depicted in **Figure 3a**. In brief, the process involves unwinding a poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET)/indium tin oxide-Ag-indium tin oxide (IMI) patterned substrate film from a roll and R2R slot-die coating of SnO_2 nanoparticles followed by annealing at 120 °C for 10 minutes in an R2R oven and rewinding it onto a roll. Then, the FAPbBr₃ perovskite was deposited by unwinding the substrate and passing it through a slot-die head, where PbBr_2 ink is deposited and dried by air-knife. Subsequently, the FABr ink is slot-die coated onto the dried PbBr_2 film, followed by 10 minutes annealing at 120 °C, and rewinding onto the roll. Considering the coating speed of 0.4 m/min and the ink flowrate of 0.3 ml/min, it takes

25 minutes to coat 7.5 ml of ink onto a substrate film of 10 meters in length and 100 mm in width. The R2R slot-die coating machine is capable of changing coating parameters such as coating speed, ink flowrate, backing roller temperature, air-knife pressure, air-knife distance and incident angle of air stream onto the web throughout the coating length. The perovskite solar cells and modules were finalized by blade coating of PEDOT: PSS hole transport layer and carbon electrode.

To achieve control over the film thicknesses and ensuring consistent quality of the FAPbBr₃ perovskite films, we first determined the wet film thickness (WFT) required to achieve the desired dry film thickness (DFT) according to the following equations:

$$WFT = \frac{Q}{W.U} \quad (1)$$

$$DFT = WFT \times \frac{c}{\rho} \quad (2)$$

Where Q is the ink flowing rate, W is width of slot-die head, U is the coating speed, c is ink concentration, and ρ is the density of dry film^[51]. Hence, the DFT can be adjusted by controlling the ink concentration, coating speed, and ink flow rate. The thickness of the blade coated film was measured with a confocal microscope to be around 380 nm as shown in **Figure S1**. Subsequently, we calculated the slot-die parameters, i.e., ink flow rate and web speed, as well as the PbBr₂ ink concentration to achieve DFT of 300-500 nm. For the two-step deposition of the perovskite in ambient air, the proper drying of the lead halide ink before the deposition of the FAPbBr₃ ink is crucial in determining the film quality of the final perovskite film^[39]. In a previous study, we had categorized the drying processes of the PbBr₂ ink into four groups: ambient, incomplete, optimized, and excessive drying^[39]. Ambient drying occurs without the aid of a hot roller or air stream, allowing the PbBr₂ ink to dry naturally in air, which can take several minutes. Incomplete drying involves the assistance of a hot roller and air stream, but the ink remains partially wet upon deposition and dries shortly afterwards, leading to a rough and whitish PbBr₂ film. Conversely, optimized drying ensures that the ink dries completely upon application, with the support of a hot roller and air stream, resulting in a smooth and fully transparent PbBr₂ film. Excessive air-knife pressure results in cross-web ribbing defects and non-uniform perovskite formation visible with naked eye. We determined the optimized drying parameters by varying the air-knife pressure and distance from the substrate as well as the roller temperature along the web during the R2R coating process (**Table S3**), until we observed fully dried and smooth PbBr₂ films. The optimized parameters were found to be an air-knife pressure of 0.1 bar, a of 7 cm of the air-knife from the substrate, and a roller temperature of 70° C.

Figure 3. (a) Schematic representation of the R2R slot-die coating process for solar cell and module fabrication. (b) Photographic and SEM images demonstrating the morphology of $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{FA}_{0.95}\text{PbBr}_3$ perovskite films using DMSO as the solvent. (c) Contact angle measurement showing the wettability of $\text{PbBr}_2 + 5\% \text{CsBr}$ ink on a PET/IMI/SnO₂ substrate using DMSO. (d) Photographic and SEM images of $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{FA}_{0.95}\text{PbBr}_3$ perovskite films fabricated with a DMSO: BuOH (9:1) solvent mixture. (e) Contact angle measurement depicting the wettability of the $\text{PbBr}_2 + 5\% \text{CsBr}$ in DMSO: BuOH on a PET/IMI/SnO₂ substrate.

2.3. Butanol Co-solvent

Visual defects were noticed in the R2R coated perovskite films as there are visible streaks and areas of different opacity throughout the film which suggests the uneven drying of ink across the substrate as shown in **Figure 3b**. The accumulation of the material is visible at the edges of the film which is referred to as edge thickening. In this case, the evaporation of DMSO occurs more rapidly at the edges because solvent vapor escapes more quickly in these areas. As a result, ink flows from the center to the edges of the film, causing the solids within the liquid to accumulate at the edges. In addition, the chatter defects, characterized by lines perpendicular to the coating direction (**Figure S2a**) are visible. These defects occur from the rapid changes in the properties of the ink during the drying process^[30,52,53].

Ink engineering is an effective approach to enhance the film quality in slot-die coating of perovskite solar cells by tuning drying dynamics, rheology, and surface energy of the precursor ink^[23,33,35,54]. We have investigated the effect of Butyl alcohol (BuOH) co-solvent to the PbBr₂ solution to modify the properties of the ink. BuOH is a non-toxic solvent, with a lower boiling point, higher vapor pressure, and a higher viscosity than DMSO. In addition, BuOH has a lower surface tension of 0.025 N/m compared to 0.043 N/m for DMSO^[55,56]. We added different percentages of BuOH to the perovskite ink, namely 5%, 10%, and 15% vol. and observed that upon using 10% BuOH as a co-solvent the ink is stable, whereas the PbBr₂ crystallizes at higher concentrations of BuOH (**Figure S3**). Consequently, we performed R2R slot-die coating with the perovskite ink of DMSO:BuOH (9:1). The contact angle was reduced from 42° to 23° by the addition of BuOH to the ink. The improved wettability of the BuOH ink suggests that the mixture has a lower surface tension and thus better compatibility with the substrate surface energy and promotes better spreading of the ink over the substrate, reducing the partial dewetting, and promoting a more uniform coating. As shown in **Figure 3d**, upon the addition of BuOH the film appeared more uniform, with fewer defects. The absorbance spectra of 12 different points across perovskite films were measured as shown in **Figure S2**, confirming the better uniformity of the DMSO:BuOH ink. The edge thickening and chatter defects were eliminated, the surface texture looks smoother, and the SEM image presents better film morphology with more uniform and well-defined grain boundaries. In addition, **Figure 3d and e** show the contact angle measurement of the inks with and without BuOH on PET/IMI/SnO₂ substrate.

Figure 4a presents PV parameters comparing devices prepared from DMSO (control) and from DMSO:BuOH (9:1) (BuOH). The champion device is obtained for the BuOH containing ink and achieves 8.97% PCE. The corresponding values of V_{OC} of 1.47 V, J_{SC} of 8.43 mA.cm⁻², and fill factor of 72.3% are significantly enhanced over those observed for the control devices, which is a clear indication of enhanced crystal quality with reduced defect density. This is further corroborated by the external quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements displayed in **Figure 4b**, which demonstrate that the BuOH devices exhibit higher current densities than the control devices, despite their lower optical densities (**Figure S2**). We also measured the dark J-V curves to understand current flows through the cells under dark conditions as it is indicative of leakage and recombination currents. The dark J-V-curve of the BuOH device shows very little leakage, but greatly enhanced injection currents in comparison to the control device. These results underscore the importance of solvent engineering in the optimization of perovskite solar cells and highlight the potential of such modifications for scalable manufacturing processes like R2R slot-die coating.

The ISOS D-1 shelf-life stability test^[57] on unencapsulated solar cells (**Figure 4d**) demonstrated that cells prepared from DMSO:BuOH ink retained 87% of their initial performance after 4,000 hours of storage at room temperature and under ambient air conditions, while control cells maintained only 75%. In addition, the light-soaking stability test was carried out for the champion device (BuOH) under LED lights with light intensities of 0.7 suns. As shown in **Figure S6** the device still delivered 80% of its initial PCE after 480-hour of testing .

Figure 4. (a) Box plots showing the PV characteristics of R2R coated PSCs ($\text{PbBr}_2 + 5\% \text{CsBr} + \text{FABr}$) deposited using DMSO (control) and DMSO:BuOH (9:1), (BuOH). (b) The corresponding EQE spectra. (c) dark JV measurements of control and BuOH. (d) ISOS D-1 shelf-life stability tests.

2.4. R2R Slot-die Coated Perovskite Solar Modules

R2R coated perovskite solar modules consisting of seven cells with 2.41 cm^2 active area each, resulting in a total active area of 16.84 cm^2 , were fabricated using the same procedure as for cells, but with a different laser scribing pattern according to our previous work^[58]. The layout is shown in **Figure 5b** and consists of seven cells that are connected in series. The cell interconnection within the module typically entails several parallel laser scribes designated as P1, P2, and P3 (**Figure 5b**).

First, flexible PET/IMI rolls were P1 laser structured using a femtosecond laser (Laser Systems GmbH) with a laser fluence of $0.40 \text{ J}/\text{cm}^2$ at a pulse duration of 350 fs and 520 nm wavelength.

This leads to the electrical isolation of the IMI bottom electrode into the number of individual cells within the flexible perovskite module. Afterward, all the functional layers of the flexible perovskite module including absorber and charge transport layers were coated on top of the P1 structured IMI substrates. Subsequently, a P2 laser line was made, which serves as a prerequisite for the electrical interconnection of adjacent cells within the module. Given the potential influence of residue, particularly during P2 scribing, it is essential to carefully remove the SnO₂ in the P2 lines. To improve the P2 interconnect lines, we investigated various laser power densities, with the goal of effectively removing the SnO₂ from the P2 lines and assuring the minimum interconnection resistance between the individual cells within the module. We carried out a series of laser power (LP) variations ranging from 650 mW to 800 mW while keeping the speed of the laser beam on the substrate constant at 6000 mm/s. **Figure S7** depicts optical microscopy images of the P2 lines thus obtained. It is clear that some perovskite residue is still present at a low LP of 650 mW. On the other hand, an LP that exceeds 800 mW runs the danger of harming the bottom conducting layer. By using an LP of around 750 mW, we were able to successfully remove SnO₂ from the P2 lines.

The P3 scribe, which runs concurrently with P1 and P2, is used to isolate the top electrode across adjacent cells and is added after the top contact has been deposited. Due to the high thickness of carbon, the P3 lines are not etched by laser ablation. To isolate the top carbon electrode, we used a stencil mask instead. The best module thus achieved provided a PCE of 5.3%. The corresponding I-V curves are presented in **Figure 5a**.

The encapsulated flexible perovskite modules were subjected to accelerated lifetime testing under damp heat conditions using ISOS-D3 (i.e., 65° module temperature and 85% relative humidity) [57]. The modules maintain approximately 80% of their initial power conversion efficiency after a 125-hour test period, and 40% of their initial stability after 350-hour test period, as shown in **Figure S8**.

Figure 5. a) The IV-curve of the R2R slot-die coated perovskite solar module. b) The photographic images of the solar module layout, P2 laser ablation, and full module.

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, R2R slot-die coating of $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{FA}_{0.95}\text{PbBr}_3$ -based wide bandgap PSCs in ambient environment is demonstrated by optimizing film formation and ink formulation. The addition of 5 mol% CsBr to FAPbBr_3 significantly improved the optoelectronic properties of the perovskite by reducing the formation of unwanted secondary phases. Additionally, using butanol as a co-solvent enhanced film morphology by reducing surface tension, which resulted in films with better uniformity, improved grain structure, and fewer defect states. These improvements have enabled a successful shift to a two-step R2R slot-die coating process, offering a feasible route for the scalable, efficient, and stable production of PSCs. The R2R coated perovskite solar cells delivered 8.97% PCE and modules fabricated with 16.84 cm^2 active-area and 5.3% PCE. Our research highlights the transformative potential of roll-to-roll (R2R) slot-die coating and ink engineering in advancing the production of perovskite solar cells (PSCs), setting the stage for their commercial success and wider use in solar energy solutions.

4. Methods

R2R Solar Cells and Modules Fabrication: The process began with the laser patterning of a roll consisting of PET/IMI with a R2R laser. Flexible PET/IMI rolls from OPVIUS GmbH were used as substrates and were P1 laser structured using a femtosecond laser (Laser Systems GmbH) with a laser fluence of 0.40 J/cm^2 at a pulse duration of 350 fs and 520 nm wavelength. This leads to the electrical isolation of the IMI bottom electrode into the number of individual cells within the flexible perovskite module. Afterwards, the laser-patterned roll is subjected to cleaning using CO_2 snow jet cleaning. The deposition of SnO_2 (2.5% wt.) is done using a R2R slot-die coater, with a flow rate set at 0.35 ml/min and a coating speed of 0.5 m/min. The roller temperature during this process was maintained at 30 °C, followed by an annealing step at 120 °C for a duration of 10 minutes in the R2R oven. The double-step deposition of the perovskite is conducted employing two sequential slot-die heads. Throughout the perovskite deposition process, various coating parameters were systematically adjusted to optimize the film quality as it is being deposited including varying the roller temperature within the range of 60-90 °C, adjusting the flow rate in the range of 0.2-0.3 ml/min, modulating the air-knife pressure within the range of 0.1-0.5 bar, and altering the air-knife distance to the wet film within the range of 4.5-7 cm. The 10 meter long roll comprised of PET/IMI/ SnO_2 / FAPbBr_3 is subsequently cut into smaller pieces for film characterization and cell fabrication. Next, PEDOT HTL-3 (Ossila) was blade-coated onto the perovskite films, employing a hot-plate temperature of 60 °C, a speed of 8 mm/s, and a gap of 150 μm . These films were then annealed at 120 °C for 5 minutes. Subsequently, the P2 laser line was scribed, which serves as a prerequisite for the electrical interconnection of every adjacent

cell within the module. Finally, carbon paste was deposited onto the samples through a glass bar coating technique, while employing a mask for precision.

Characterizations: All cells/modules were measured for their initial (t_0) performance using a class AAA solar simulator (LOT Quantum Design) before the encapsulation. For the damp-heat test, modules were encapsulated inside a barrier foil from Mitsubishi Chemicals (VD-K3DA) with a UV cut-off filter (<1% transmittance below 378 nm) and a WVTR values of 5×10^{-3} g/m²/ day. The barrier foil has a transmittance of 78% @550 nm. The module was laminated between the barrier foils using epoxy-based adhesive from DELO (Katiobond LP655), which was subsequently cured with UVA (~400 nm light) for five minutes. The entire encapsulation process was carried out under inert conditions using rim type encapsulation.

To deposit the perovskite layer for In-situ characterization, a 1 M solution of PbBr₂ in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was blade-coated with a speed of 3 mm/s, a hot-plate temperature of 60 °C, and a gap of 100 μm on glass microslides. CsBr additive is introduced into the PbBr₂ ink, with molar ratios of 0 mol%, 5 mol%, 10 mol%, and 15 mol%. To further enhance solvent extraction and film formation, a dry air knife is employed. Subsequently, FABr 0.5 M solution in isopropanol is doctor bladed with a speed of 3 mm/s, a hot-plate temperature of 60 °C, and a gap of 100 μm. Then, the films were annealed at 80 °C for 10 minutes. An experimental setup developed in-house is employed to measure the photoluminescence and absorption spectra of the films comprised of AVANTES ULS2048XL spectrometer, a 450 nm laser diode, a plano-convex lens above the substrate, and a 550 nm long-pass filter. This measurement occurred concurrently with the coating of FABr onto the PbBr₂ layer.

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References

- [1] K. Dey, B. Roose, S. D. Stranks, *Adv. Mater.* **2021**, *33*, e2102300.
- [2] L. Chouhan, S. Ghimire, C. Subrahmanyam, T. Miyasaka, V. Biju, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2020**, *49*, 2869.

- [3] P. Čulík, K. Brooks, C. Momblona, M. Adams, S. Kinge, F. Maréchal, P. J. Dyson, M. K. Nazeeruddin, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2022**, *7*, 3039.
- [4] N. Kwon, J. Lee, M. J. Ko, Y. Y. Kim, J. Seo, *Nano Converg.* **2023**, *10*, 28.
- [5] T. Druffel, *Meet. Abstr.* **2022**, *MA2022-02*, 834.
- [6] M. A. Green, E. D. Dunlop, M. Yoshita, N. Kopidakis, K. Bothe, G. Siefer, X. Hao, *Prog. Photovolt.* **2024**, *32*, 3.
- [7] Q. Fu, A. K. Y. Jen, *Next Energy* **2023**, *1*, 100004.
- [8] S. Gholipour, M. Saliba, in *Characterization Techniques for Perovskite Solar Cell Materials*, Elsevier, **2020**, pp. 1–22.
- [9] F. Matteocci, D. Rossi, L. A. Castriotta, D. Ory, S. Mejaouri, M. A. der Maur, F. Sauvage, S. Cacovich, A. Di Carlo, *Nano Energy* **2022**, *101*, 107560.
- [10] J. Barichello, D. Di Girolamo, E. Nonni, B. Paci, A. Generosi, M. Kim, A. Levtchenko, S. Cacovich, A. Di Carlo, F. Matteocci, *Sol. RRL* **2023**, *7*, 2200739.
- [11] H. Zhu, W. Wu, Y. Wu, D. Zhang, H. Zhan, Y. Cheng, L. Wang, C. Qin, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2023**, 2202827.
- [12] W. Yue, H. Yang, H. Cai, Y. Xiong, T. Zhou, Y. Liu, J. Zhao, F. Huang, Y.-B. Cheng, J. Zhong, *Adv. Mater.* **2023**, e2301548.
- [13] D. Di Girolamo, G. Vidon, J. Barichello, F. Di Giacomo, F. Jafarzadeh, B. Paci, A. Generosi, M. Kim, L. A. Castriotta, M. Frégnaux, J.-F. Guillemoles, F. Brunetti, P. Schulz, D. Ory, S. Cacovich, A. Di Carlo, F. Matteocci, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2024**, DOI 10.1002/aenm.202400663.
- [14] J. G. Cerrillo, A. Distler, F. Matteocci, K. Forberich, M. Wagner, R. Basu, L. A. Castriotta, F. Jafarzadeh, F. Brunetti, F. Yang, N. Li, A. N. C. Mendoza, A. Di Carlo, C. J. Brabec, H.-J. Egelhaaf, *Sol. RRL* **2023**, DOI 10.1002/solr.202300767.
- [15] Q. Li, Y. Zheng, X. Guo, G. Zhang, G. Ding, Y. Shi, F. Li, M. Sun, Y. Shao, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2023**, DOI 10.1002/adfm.202303729.
- [16] V. Milotti, S. Cacovich, D. R. Ceratti, D. Ory, J. Barichello, F. Matteocci, A. Di Carlo, P. M. Sheverdyeva, P. Schulz, P. Moras, *Small Methods* **2023**, *7*, DOI 10.1002/smtd.202300222.
- [17] H. Huang, H. Yuan, K. P. F. Janssen, G. Solís-Fernández, Y. Wang, C. Y. X. Tan, D. Jonckheere, E. Debroye, J. Long, J. Hendrix, J. Hofkens, J. A. Steele, M. B. J. Roeffaers, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2018**, *3*, 755.
- [18] T. Nie, Z. Fang, X. Ren, Y. Duan, S. F. Liu, *Nanomicro Lett.* **2023**, *15*, 70.
- [19] J. Yang, E. L. Lim, L. Tan, Z. Wei, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2022**, *12*, DOI 10.1002/aenm.202270122.
- [20] Y. Ma, Q. Zhao, *J. Energy Chem.* **2022**, *64*, 538.
- [21] S. Chen, X. Xiao, H. Gu, J. Huang, *Science Advances* **2021**, *7*, 1.
- [22] L. A. Castriotta, F. Matteocci, L. Vesce, L. Cinà, A. Agresti, S. Pescetelli, A. Ronconi, M. Löffler, M. M. Stylianakis, F. Di Giacomo, P. Mariani, M. Stefanelli, E. M. Speller, A. Alfano, B. Paci, A. Generosi, F. Di Fonzo, A. Petrozza, B. Rellinghaus, E. Kymakis, A. Di Carlo, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2021**, *13*, 11741.
- [23] J. Li, J. Dagar, O. Shargaieva, O. Maus, M. Remec, Q. Emery, M. Khenkin, C. Ulbrich, F. Akhundova, J. A. Márquez, T. Unold, M. Fenske, C. Schultz, B. Stegemann, A. Al-Ashouri, S. Albrecht, A. T. Esteves, L. Korte, H. Köbler, A. Abate, D. M. Töbrens, I. Zizak, E. J. W. List-Kratochvil, R. Schlattmann, E. Unger, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2023**, 2203898.

- [24] D. Beynon, E. Parvazian, K. Hooper, J. McGettrick, R. Patidar, T. Dunlop, Z. Wei, P. Davies, R. Garcia-Rodriguez, M. Carnie, M. Davies, T. Watson, *Adv. Mater.* **2023**, e2208561.
- [25] F. Schackmar, H. Eggers, M. Frericks, B. S. Richards, U. Lemmer, G. Hernandez-Sosa, U. W. Paetzold, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2021**, 6, DOI 10.1002/admt.202000271.
- [26] C. Chen, J. Chen, H. Han, L. Chao, J. Hu, T. Niu, H. Dong, S. Yang, Y. Xia, Y. Chen, W. Huang, *Nature* **2022**, 612, 266.
- [27] C. Chen, C. Ran, Q. Yao, J. Wang, C. Guo, L. Gu, H. Han, X. Wang, L. Chao, Y. Xia, Y. Chen, *Adv. Sci. (Weinh.)* **2023**, 10, e2303992.
- [28] J. E. Bishop, C. D. Read, J. A. Smith, T. J. Routledge, D. G. Lidzey, *Sci. Rep.* **2020**, 10, 1.
- [29] L.-H. Chou, J. M. W. Chan, C.-L. Liu, *Sol. RRL* **2022**, 6, 2101035.
- [30] A. Agresti, F. Di Giacomo, S. Pescetelli, A. Di Carlo, *Nano Energy* **2024**, 122, 109317.
- [31] C. S. Pathak, H. Choi, H. Kim, J. Lim, S.-K. Cho, D. S. Ham, S. Song, *Sol. RRL* **2023**, DOI 10.1002/solr.202300860.
- [32] Y. Ma, Z. Lu, X. Su, G. Zou, Q. Zhao, *Adv. Energy Sustain. Res.* **2023**, 4, 2200133.
- [33] Y. Galagan, F. Di Giacomo, H. Gorter, G. Kirchner, I. de Vries, R. Andriessen, P. Groen, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2018**, 8, 1801935.
- [34] M. Othman, F. Zheng, A. Seeber, A. S. R. Chesman, A. D. Scully, K. P. Ghiggino, M. Gao, J. Etheridge, D. Angmo, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2021**, 2110700.
- [35] J. Li, J. Dagar, O. Shargaieva, M. A. Flatken, H. Köbler, M. Fenske, C. Schultz, B. Stegemann, J. Just, D. M. Többens, A. Abate, R. Munir, E. Unger, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2021**, 11, 2003460.
- [36] H. M. Cronin, K. D. G. I. Jayawardena, Z. Stoeva, M. Shkunov, S. R. P. Silva, *Nanotechnology* **2017**, 28, 114004.
- [37] L. Nakka, W. Luo, A. G. Aberle, F. Lin, *Sol. RRL* **2023**, DOI 10.1002/solr.202300100.
- [38] Z. Yang, C.-C. Chueh, F. Zuo, J. H. Kim, P.-W. Liang, A. K.-Y. Jen, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2015**, 5, 1500328.
- [39] F. Jafarzadeh, L. A. Castriotta, F. De Rossi, J. Ali, F. Di Giacomo, A. Di Carlo, F. Matteocci, F. Brunetti, *Sustain. Energy Fuels* **2023**, 7, 2219.
- [40] J. Zhang, T. Bu, J. Li, H. Li, Y. Mo, Z. Wu, Y. Liu, X. L. Zhang, Y. B. Cheng, F. Huang, *J. Mater. Chem. A Mater. Energy Sustain.* **2020**, 8, 8447.
- [41] W. Shao, H. Wang, F. Ye, C. Wang, C. Wang, H. Cui, K. Dong, Y. Ge, T. Wang, W. Ke, G. Fang, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2023**, 16, 252.
- [42] F. Matteocci, L. Vesce, F. U. Kosasih, L. A. Castriotta, S. Cacovich, A. L. Palma, G. Divitini, C. Ducati, A. Di Carlo, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, 11, 25195.
- [43] N.-G. Park, *Nat. Sustain.* **2020**, 4, 192.
- [44] S. K. Podapangi, F. Jafarzadeh, S. Mattiello, T. B. Korukonda, A. Singh, L. Beverina, T. M. Brown, *RSC Adv.* **2023**, 13, 18165.
- [45] "Regulation - 2021/2030 - EN - EUR-Lex," can be found under <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/2030/oj>, n.d.
- [46] R. Vidal, J.-A. Alberola-Borràs, S. N. Habisreutinger, J.-L. Gimeno-Molina, D. T. Moore, T. H. Schloemer, I. Mora-Seró, J. J. Berry, J. M. Luther, *Nature Sustainability* **2021**, 4, 277.
- [47] L. Yang, K. Wei, Z. Xu, F. Li, R. Chen, X. Zheng, X. Cheng, T. Jiang, *Opt. Lett.* **2018**, 43, 122.
- [48] N. Zhou, Y. Shen, Y. Zhang, Z. Xu, G. Zheng, L. Li, Q. Chen, H. Zhou, *Small* **2017**, 13, DOI 10.1002/smll.201700484.

- [49] G. Tong, T. Chen, H. Li, W. Song, Y. Chang, J. Liu, L. Yu, J. Xu, Y. Qi, Y. Jiang, *Sol. RRL* **2019**, *3*, 1900030.
- [50] C. Otero-Martínez, M. Imran, N. J. Schrenker, J. Ye, K. Ji, A. Rao, S. D. Stranks, R. L. Z. Hoye, S. Bals, L. Manna, J. Pérez-Juste, L. Polavarapu, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed Engl.* **2022**, *61*, DOI 10.1002/anie.202205617.
- [51] H. Benkreira, J. B. Ikin, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **2016**, *150*, 66.
- [52] C. Teixeira, R. Fuentes-Pineda, L. Andrade, A. Mendes, D. Forgács, *Mater. Adv.* **2023**, *4*, 3863.
- [53] E. A. Ramírez, J. P. Velásquez, A. Flórez, J. F. Montoya, R. Betancur, F. Jaramillo, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* **2023**, *25*, DOI 10.1002/adem.202200964.
- [54] S.-H. Huang, C.-K. Guan, P.-H. Lee, H.-C. Huang, C.-F. Li, Y.-C. Huang, W.-F. Su, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *10*, 2001567.
- [55] K. K. Cheng, C. Park, *Heat Mass Transf.* **2017**, *53*, 2255.
- [56] H. L. Clever, C. C. Snead, *J. Phys. Chem.* **1963**, *67*, 918.
- [57] M. V. Khenkin, E. A. Katz, A. Abate, G. Bardizza, J. J. Berry, C. Brabec, F. Brunetti, V. Bulović, Q. Burlingame, A. Di Carlo, R. Cheacharoen, Y.-B. Cheng, A. Colsmann, S. Cros, K. Domanski, M. Dusza, C. J. Fell, S. R. Forrest, Y. Galagan, D. Di Girolamo, M. Grätzel, A. Hagfeldt, E. von Hauff, H. Hoppe, J. Kettle, H. Köbler, M. S. Leite, S. Liu, Y.-L. Loo, J. M. Luther, C.-Q. Ma, M. Madsen, M. Manceau, M. Matheron, M. McGehee, R. Meitzner, M. K. Nazeeruddin, A. F. Nogueira, Ç. Odabaşı, A. Osherov, N.-G. Park, M. O. Reese, F. De Rossi, M. Saliba, U. S. Schubert, H. J. Snaith, S. D. Stranks, W. Tress, P. A. Troshin, V. Turkovic, S. Veenstra, I. Visoly-Fisher, A. Walsh, T. Watson, H. Xie, R. Yildirim, S. M. Zakeeruddin, K. Zhu, M. Lira-Cantu, *Nat. Energy* **2020**, *5*, 35.
- [58] L. Dong, S. Qiu, J. G. Cerrillo, M. Wagner, O. Kasian, S. Feroze, D. Jang, C. Li, V. M. L. Corre, K. Zhang, H. Peisert, F. U. Kosasih, C. Arrive, T. Du, F. Yang, C. J. Brabec, H.-J. Egelhaaf, *arXiv [cond-mat.mtrl-sci]* **2024**.

Supporting Information

Table S1. The peak positions of the three major planes in XRD patterns of FAPbBr₃ films with the addition of CsBr.

No.	Miller Index	Peak Position (°)			
		FAPbBr ₃	CsBr 5%	CsBr 10%	CsBr 15%
1	[100]	14.7647	14.7680	14.7827	14.8245
2	[110]	20.9598	21.0136	20.9835	21.1077
3	[200]	29.7954	29.8377	29.8778	29.9648

Figure S1. Confocal microscopy image of blade coated FAPbBr₃ film on glass slide and a laser scribed line to measure the thickness of the film.

a)

b)

Figure S2. Photographic images of a portion of the R2R coated PSCs deposited and corresponding spatially resolved UV-Vis Absorption spectra. a) DMSO and b) DMSO:BuOH (9:1).

Figure S3. The photographic image of $\text{PbBr}_2\text{-(CsBr)}_{0.05}$ in DMSO, DMSO+ 5% BuOH, DMSO+ 10% BuOH, and DMSO+ 15% BuOH. The crystallization of precursor is visible when 15% BuOH is present as co-solvent.

Figure S4. a) JV-curves of the best obtained R2R slot-die coated solar cells with DMSO solvent (control) and DMSO:BuOH solvent (BuOH).

Table S2. PV characteristics of the best obtained solar cells from DMSO ink (control) and from DMSO:BuOH ink (BuOH).

Type	Direction	V _{oc} (V)	J _{sc} (mA.cm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)
Control	FW	1.23	7.40	52.7	4.80
	RV	1.33	7.25	64.5	6.20
BuOH	FW	1.30	8.39	60.0	6.57
	RV	1.47	8.43	72.3	8.97

Figure S5. Absorption spectra of FAPbBr₃ films with different CsBr concentrations.

Table S3. The variation of R2R slot-die coating parameters along the coating process to achieve optimized drying of PbBr₂ films.

Var.	Air Pressure (bar)	Air Stream Distance (cm)	Ink Flow Rate (ml/min)	Roll Temp. (°C)	Drying Status	Description
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1	0.5	4.5	0.2	70	Excessive Drying	High air pressure, short air-stream distance.
2s	0.1	7	0.2	80	Optimized Drying	
3	0.1	7	0.3	80	Partial Drying	Higher ink flow rate resulted in partial drying.
4	0.1	7	0.3	90	Optimized Drying	

Figure S6. The light-soaking stability test of the champion solar cell encapsulated with a Kapton tape.

Figure S7. Optical Microscopic Images of P2 Laser ablation lines with different laser powers.

Figure S8. The damp heat stability test (ISOS D-3) of the encapsulated modules stored inside an environmental chamber at 65 °C and 85% RH and the photograph of the encapsulated module.